

Variation in Stability and Conductivity of Chromium Tellurate Sol during Coagulation at Various Stages of Dialysis

K. T. Mandloi* and S. H. Banerji

Chromium tellurate sol has been prepared and the changes in stability and conductivity of the sol during coagulation at different stages of dialysis have been determined. The $(K_m - K_e)$ value gives the excess of conductivity of the mixture of sol and electrolyte, (K_m) , over that of the electrolyte alone, (K_e) . $(K_m - K_e)$ decreases at all stages of purity of the sol but is positive in a pure sol and becomes gradually negative in purer stages of the sol with increasing concentration of the electrolyte. Co-precipitation and penetration into double layer of coagulating ions seems to account for this.

It is well known that adsorption of solvent molecules and peptising ions are two main factors in the stability of lyophilic colloids and that the latter are coagulated by electrolytes. The study of coagulation has two aspects; first a study of phenomenon as to how different electrolytes affect different sols and secondly, a thorough understanding of the physico-chemical changes involved in the mechanism of coagulation.

Rai and Ghosh¹ studied the effect of adding progressively increasing amounts of electrolyte to hydrated ferric oxide and other sols. They found that the electrical conductivity in excess of that of the electrolyte decreased. This decrease in conductivity continued beyond the coagulation point. They explained their results by assuming that the added anions neutralised positive charges on the sol. This allowed additional H^+ ions to be adsorbed and lower the concentration of the latter in the solution till finally the surface was covered with H^+ ions and more anions caused coagulation. Further in a highly disperse system, the Helmholtz layer is fainter due to large displacement arising out of Brownian movement. For larger units, however, the double layer becomes denser contributing lesser conductivity.

By far the most universal and dominant factor in the stability of sols is the electric charge on the colloid particles. Hence a conductometric study gives an insight into the physico-chemical changes taking place in the disperse system during coagulation. The study of coagulation of chromium tellurate has been undertaken with a view to investigate the opinions expressed above with regard to the charge on colloid particles, stability of the sols and changes taking place during coagulation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chromium tellurate sol was prepared by mixing 0.5% potassium tellurate solution with 13.0929% of chromium chloride solution in the ratio of 11:1 by volume and kept for dialysis. Water was changed every 24 hr.

*Present Address: Assistant Professor of Chemistry, Govt. College, Shahdol (M.P.)

1. Rai R.S. and Ghosh S., *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1954, 23, 48, 142; 1956, 25, 190; *Kolloid-Z* 14¹ 1955, 142, 104.

All the conductivity measurements were carried out at $25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ with Mullard's Conductivity Bridge using Doran Oscillator.

Standard methods were used for the determination of the composition of the sol at various stages of dialysis. Tellurate was estimated by reduction to tellurium with hydrazine hydrochloride and saturated sulphur dioxide solution⁶. Chromium was determined volumetrically by oxidation with sodium peroxide and titration with standardised ferrous ammonium sulphate solution, using diphenylamine as an indicator. Chloride estimation was carried out by Vohlard's method.

TABLE I

Variation in $(K_m - K_s)$ in $\text{mohs} \times 10^3$ during coagulation at various stages of dialysis for chromium tellurate sol.

No of days of dialysis	1	4	7	10	13	16	19	23
Composi- tion of TeO_4^{--} Sol.	Cr^{+++} 0.1984% Cl^- 0.3644%	0.1545% 0.2135%	0.1136% 0.1062%	0.0888% 0.0849%	0.0642% 0.0738%	0.0528% 0.0686%	0.0476% 0.0669%	0.0445% 0.0625%
Conc. in gm. mol per Litre.	0.02 M K_2SO_4	0.0075 M K_2SO_4	0.0060 M K_2SO_4	0.0032 M K_2SO_4	0.0028 M K_2SO_4	0.0025 M K_2SO_4	0.0020 M K_2SO_4	0.0014 M K_2SO_4
Vol. in ml.								
0	4.0880	1.9620	1.0350	0.5777	0.3652	0.2133	0.1177	0.0714
2	3.6680	1.7710	0.8721	0.4877	0.2889	0.1444	0.0660	0.0283
4	3.3130	1.5530	0.7663	0.4191	0.2371	0.0954	0.0020	-0.0196
6	2.9970	1.4170	0.6267	0.3516	0.1799	0.0436	-0.0256	-0.0474
8	2.6160	1.2760	0.5177	0.2997	0.1117	-0.0053	-0.0600	-0.0850
10	2.2890	1.1930	0.4142	0.2208	0.0491	-0.0654	-0.1008	-0.1201
12	1.9650	0.9974	0.2997	0.1690	-0.0191	-0.0981	-0.1265	-0.1504
14	1.6900	0.8557	0.2017	0.1090	-0.0318	-0.1199	-0.1581	-0.1808
16	1.3360	0.7389	0.1090	0.0818	-0.0600	-0.1690	-0.1799	* -0.2116
18	0.9811	0.6267	0.0373	0.0164	-0.0981	-0.1907	-0.2071	* -0.2382
20	0.8176	0.4921	-0.0179	-0.0218	-0.1236	-0.2125	-0.2289	** -0.2601

*Gelation starts

**Gel formation

RESULTS

From the table I and figure I for specific conductivity concentration curves, it is clear that with increasing amounts of K_2SO_4 , the specific conductivity decreases continuously. Further, when the sol is impure, the specific conductivity decreases, but is still positive; as, however, the sol becomes purer and purer, though at smaller concentrations of K_2SO_4 , the specific conductivity is positive, it becomes negative at higher concentrations of K_2SO_4 .

DISCUSSION

In a single binary electrolyte, the total conductivity of the solution is the sum of the conductivities of the constituent ions. If, however, salts are added to poly-

electrolytes, the total conductance of this arbitrary mixture of ions is observed to be not equal to the sum of the individual conductivities as measured in simple binary solutions; it is actually less. This has been shown experimentally and worked out theoretically by Onsager and Fuoss³. Thus one of the factors causing the decrease in conductivity of the chromium tellurate sol is the salt effect.

Changes in specific conductivity of chromium tellurate sol with the addition of K₂SO₄ at various stages of dialysis.

FIG. 1

The other factors responsible for the decrease in conductivity must be change in charge, size and even shape of the colloidal micelle, for increasing amounts of electrolyte. K₂SO₄ lead to progressive agglomeration and flocculation. The reduction of charge may be due to replacement of aquo groups from the colloidal micelle by hydrogen ions², and also on account of compression of the double layer by added electrolyte and consequent immobilisation of ions in the double layer⁴. Besides removal of ions by coprecipitation^{5,6,7,8} may also be responsible for decrease of the charge in and conductivity of the solution. An increase in size and change in shape from sphere will make for low mobility and conductivity.

The action of varying amounts of electrolyte added to a sol may be visualised as follows: When an electrolyte is added to a sol, it will exhibit the natural tendency to diffuse and equalise its concentration throughout the dispersion medium. This process would be similar to the mixing of electrolyte solutions in so far as the bulk of the medium far away from the colloidal particles is concerned. When, however, the component ions of the added electrolyte approach the micelle, these have to face the diffuse ionic double

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5. Yadav, B.P. and Chatterji A.C., *Proc. Ind. Sc. Congr.*, 1941, 28, 54.

6. Reiman, W. Nuss J. D. and Naiman B., *Quantitative Analysis*, p. 249. McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, 1951.

7. Koltzoff and Moskovits: *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 629.

8. Reiman, W., Nuss J. D., and Naiman B. *Quantitative Analysis*, p. 250. McGraw Hill Book Co., New York 1951.

layer. Thus a certain fraction of them will mix up in the outer diffuse atmosphere of ions, "counter ions". So far as the SO_4 ions (the coagulating ions) are concerned, these will be repelled by counter ions in the outer part of the double layer and attracted by the particles.

These coagulating (SO_4) ions have a tendency to desorb and remove the oppositely charged peptising ions either as an undissociated compound or into the bulk of the dispersion medium due electrostatic attraction. But in order to desorb these peptising ions, the coagulating ions have also to work in deforming the solvated hull in the case of lyophilic sols. Hence only a certain fraction of the total concentration of coagulating ions can and do succeed in desorbing the peptising ions. Again in view of Langmuir's theory of chemisorption⁹ and Van't Hoff's theory of dilute solutions, it would not be altogether absurd to postulate a dynamic equilibrium between ions desorbed on the colloid particles and those present in the diffuse layer.

Now, when only a small amount of K_2SO_4 is added, a certain fraction of potassium ions find their way into the diffuse ionic layer and the rest into the bulk of the dispersion medium. So far as coagulating SO_4 ions are concerned, at these low concentrations only a fraction can penetrate and that too in the complex diffuse ionic layer and the rest remain in dispersion medium. Thus there will be practically no coagulation. As the concentration of K_2SO_4 increases, more *similions* (K^+) and coagulating (SO_4) ions even succeed in desorbing some of the peptising ions (Cr^{+++}) which get into the bulk of the dispersion medium. Thus some active centres on the sol particles are released. A few of them may take up hydroxinium ions (exchange adsorption) from the solvent, but some will be free to attach to an approaching colloid particles and coalesce. The presence of K^+ and SO_4^{--} ions in the diffuse layer will neutralise partially the repulsive forces due to counter ions (Cl^-) and also the peptising ions i.e., reduce the surface potential and help agglomeration. The aggregation of sol particles leads to an increase in their size and viscosity of the system and decrease in mobility and charge. Thus there will be decrease in the conductivity of the sol ($K_m - K_e$). The desorbed peptising ions, equivalent to coagulating ions will also cause a decrease in conductivity due to salt effects³. With a further increase in concentration of electrolyte the active centres of sol particles released for agglomeration are relatively more and this would cause a loose, irregular flock to be formed, which will coprecipitate³⁻⁵ some of the coagulating ion and cause decrease in conductivity. The amount of K_2SO_4 in excess of the concentration necessary for rapid coagulation, simply go to reduce surface potential and hence the stability.

Incidentally, the above concept, explains Ostwald's theory¹¹ according to which the stability of the sol is influenced by the electrostatic structure of the medium. Further gel information instead of normal flocculation on the addition of the electrolyte to relatively pure sol, also follows from the above views since in a purer sol, electrolyte can release several active centres on majority of the particles leading to rapid agglomeration into a three dimensional structure with medium immobilised into it.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY OF SAUGAR,
SAGAR, M.P. (INDIA)

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